

Comparison of Fibreoptic guided Endotracheal intubation versus Video Laryngoscope in cases with Difficult airway

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Abstract

Background: FFS and the videolaryngoscope have become recognized as useful instruments in the context of airway management in recent years. Because it provides superior laryngeal vision, improves the chances of a successful first try, and lowers the risk of complications, the videolaryngoscope is frequently chosen over the conventional laryngoscope. With these in view this observational study was conducted to compare the effectiveness of the flexible fiberoptic technique with the videolaryngoscope approach in light of these premises and the gap in the literature.

Methods: This comparative analytical study was conducted in the department of Anesthesiology among the cases underwent surgical procedure under GA at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Institute during November 2024 to April 2025. A total of sixty cases were included in the study. Group F underwent Flexible fiberoptic scope and group V underwent video laryngoscopy with 30 cases in each group. Analysis was done using SPSS 19.

Results: Both group F and group V were similar in demographic profile. Mean time taken for intubation was lesser in group F compared to group V without altering hemodynamic parameters and much adverse effects.

Conclusion: This study showed that FFS is a very safe, effective, and repeatable method for managing airways compared to video laryngoscopy. This method has proven very helpful even in situations of unexpected difficulties since it requires less time and can be used to a wide range of patient characteristics. By reducing bleeding and tissue damage, the approach helps to optimize surgical circumstances and is especially helpful in instances with complicated anatomy.

Key words: video laryngoscopy, flexible fiberoptic scope, difficult intubation

Introduction

In both elective and emergency settings, airway control is a basic and difficult component of anesthesiology practice. The handling of a challenging airway is one of the most important and intricate situations, and even the most skilled anesthetist may run into issues using the common tools like face masks, laryngoscopes, and supraglottic devices. American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) revised recommendations¹ offer a framework for handling these circumstances, differentiating between two scenarios: unexpected difficult intubation and expected difficult intubation. However, these guidelines highlight the use of advanced devices like rigid laryngoscopic blades, videolaryngoscopes, flexible fiberoscopes (FFS), supraglottic devices, and rigid bronchoscopes, or a combination of these, and outline various options for intubation of the trachea, like awake or anesthetized tracheal intubation. In severe situations, invasive treatments like Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO) or cricothyrotomy could be necessary². Naturally, patient-specific parameters including age, BMI, airway morphology, comorbidities, and the anesthetist's professional proficiency are just as important to the effective treatment of challenging airways as the availability of cutting-edge equipment. This emphasizes how each case is different and how complicated they are, especially when there is an urgent situation and the stakes are high. Difficult airway care is still linked to a high risk of consequences, such as airway damage, hypoxia, anoxia, and even death, even with the latest recommendations and technology developments.

The importance of airway control outside of the surgical context has also been demonstrated by recent data. In patients with brain injuries, for instance, pre-hospital intubation using an endotracheal tube has been linked to a lower risk of morbidity and death. This highlights the vital significance of prompt and efficient airway control in highly hazardous clinical situations, even outside of the operating room³. FFS and the videolaryngoscope have become recognized as useful instruments in the context of airway management in recent years. Because it provides superior laryngeal vision, improves the chances of a successful first try, and lowers the risk of complications, the videolaryngoscope is frequently chosen over the conventional laryngoscope^{4,5}. Because it allows for precise laryngeal vision, reduces damage, and makes it easier to position the ET correctly, FFS has shown itself to be a useful technique in these difficult situations^{6,7}. Additionally, using these two technologies together has become more popular recently as a novel intubation method (combined approach). In fact, it makes use of both technologies' advantages, improving control, visibility, and accuracy when traversing the airway and placing the ET. This method is particularly useful in cases like head and neck operations, bariatric procedures, burn cases, and polytrauma where direct vision and manipulation of the airway are restricted because of anatomical or pathological issues. Studies examining its application, particularly under general anesthesia in head and neck procedures, are few, despite the rising interest in this combination method⁸⁻¹⁰. This observational study aims to compare the effectiveness of the flexible fiberoptic technique with the videolaryngoscope approach in light of these premises and the gap in the literature.

Methods

This comparative analytical study was conducted in the department of Anesthesiology among the cases underwent surgical procedure under GA at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Institute during November 2024 to April 2025. Adult cases from both genders with ASA class I and class II were included. Cases with mouth opening < 20 mm and poor dental

status were excluded. A total of sixty cases were included in the study. Group F underwent Flexible fiberoptic scope and group V underwent video laryngoscopy with 30 cases in each group. Pre anesthetic evaluation was done for all cases.

All cases underwent adequate pre-op assessment on the day of surgery iv access was established monitoring system was applied. Cases were pre oxygenated and anaesthetized. Depolarising muscle relaxant was given. An assistant performed jaw thrust to expand the oropharyngeal space in fibreoptic intubation. The time of intubation was calculated from removal of facemask to inflation of cuff. ETT placement was confirmed with capnography and bilateral auscultation. In video laryngoscopy similarly the time of removal of mask and inflation of cuff was documented. Spo₂ and Pulse rate were monitored and recorded. Analysis was done using SPSS 19. Chi square test and Independent sample t test were used. P value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

In this present study the mean age among group F participants was 46.7±14.3 years and group V participants was 44.8±15.2 years, there was no difference noted to be significant between the groups for age (p value =0.638). Similarly gender distribution between the groups was also noted to be insignificant with p value of 0.739. Among group F cases 20% of them were in class I ASA and 30% of them were in class II ASA similarly in group V 16.7% of them were in class I ASA and 33.3% of the cases were in class II ASA with no association between the groups for ASA classification, p value was insignificant. The mean BMI among group F cases were 26.8±2.6 and group V cases were 27.2±2.8, the difference in mean BMI between group F and V was statistically insignificant (p value =0.792). In this study based on the surgical procedure there was no significant association noted between the groups where p value was recorded to be 0.561.

Table 1: Clinical profile of cases

Variables	Group F	Group V	p value
Mean age (in years)	46.7±14.3	44.8±15.2	0.638
Gender			
Male	22 (36.7)	19 (31.7)	0.739
Female	8 (13.3)	11 (18.3)	
ASA class			
Class 1	12 (20)	10 (16.7)	0.835
Class 2	18 (30)	20 (33.3)	
Mean BMI	26.8±2.6	27.2±2.8	0.792
Surgical procedure			
General Surgery	6 (10)	10 (16.7)	0.561
Orthopedics	10 (16.7)	8 (13.3)	
ENT	5 (8.3)	6 (10)	
OBGY	9 (15)	6 (10)	

The mean time taken for intubation among group F participants was 8.1 ± 2.6 secs and among group V participants was 10.3 ± 3.5 secs. The difference in mean time duration for intubation was statistically significant with p value 0.0076. The number of attempts for intubation was one among 48.3% of the cases and two attempts among 1.7% of the cases each in both the groups with insignificant association between the cases in both the groups.

Table 2: Comparison of Parameters of Intubation between groups

Parameter	Group F	Group V	p value
Mean time taken for intubation (in secs)	8.1 ± 2.6	10.3 ± 3.5	0.0076*
Number of intubation attempts			
One	29 (48.3)	29 (48.3)	1.000
Two	1 (1.7)	1 (1.7)	

*Significant

The mean Heart Rate, Mean Arterial Pressure and SpO₂ between the groups at baseline, at insertion of ET tube, after 5 mins, after 10 mins and after 15 mins for group F and group V are shown in the table.

Table 3: Comparison of Hemodynamic parameters between groups

Parameters	Group F	Group V
HR		
Baseline	78.4 ± 4.8	76.4 ± 5.1
At insertion	79.4 ± 6.3	78.9 ± 7.1
After 5 mins	77.5 ± 6.0	79.6 ± 6.4
After 10 mins	76.5 ± 4.2	78.8 ± 5.3
After 15 mins	76.4 ± 5.4	76.6 ± 4.7
MAP		
Baseline	69.4 ± 5.4	69.3 ± 4.9
At insertion	69.8 ± 5.1	69.2 ± 5.9
After 5 mins	69.9 ± 4.7	69.1 ± 4.6
After 10 mins	69.8 ± 5.7	68.8 ± 4.7
After 15 mins	68.3 ± 5.5	67.9 ± 5.1
SpO₂		
Baseline	98.3 ± 1.2	98.2 ± 1.5
At insertion	98.3 ± 1.1	98.5 ± 1.3
After 5 mins	98.2 ± 1.2	98.3 ± 1.4
After 10 mins	98.3 ± 1.4	98.5 ± 1.0
After 15 mins	98.6 ± 1.1	98.4 ± 1.2

On assessing the adverse effects staining of device was noted among 5% of the cases in group V with insignificant statistical association between group F and V cases (p value =0.075). Vomiting was present among 3.3% of the cases in group F and 3.3% of the cases in group V with no statistical association (p value =1.000). Sore throat was reported among 1.7% of the cases in group F and 3.3% of the cases in group V were no statistical association was recorded (p value =0.553). Oral bleeding was noted among 3.3% of the case sin group V while no cases in group F had oral bleed with no significant association between the groups for oral bleeding (p value =0.151). Dysphagia was found among 1.7% of the cases in F group and 5% of the cases in V group with insignificant association between the group participants (p value =0.301).

Table 4: Comparison of adverse effects between groups

Adverse effects	Group F	Group V	p value
Staining of device			
Present	0 (0)	3 (5)	0.075
Absent	30 (50)	27 (45)	
Vomiting			
Present	2 (3.3)	2 (3.3)	1.000
Absent	28 (46.7)	28 (46.7)	
Sore Throat			
Present	1 (1.7)	2 (3.3)	0.553
Absent	29 (48.3)	28 (46.7)	
Oral Bleeding			
Present	0 (0)	2 (3.3)	0.151
Absent	30 (50)	28 (46.7)	
Dysphagia			
Present	1 (1.7)	3 (5)	0.301
Absent	29 (48.3)	27 (45)	

Discussion

According to Arulkumaran N et al¹¹, there was no difference between first pass intubation with VL and DL. In the intensive care unit, VL led to more first-pass intubations than DL, and this trend was also observed in the emergency room or pre-hospital context. First-pass intubations were better with the CMAC than with the DL, although they were comparable with the Glide Scope. First-pass intubation with VL was higher among novice/trainee clinicians than with DL, but not among paramedics/nurses or experienced clinicians. During trauma or cardiac resuscitation, there was no disparity in first pass intubation between VL and DL. VL was linked to higher arterial hypotension but fewer oesophageal intubations than DL. In conclusion, VL is linked to a higher rate of first pass rescue intubation in ICU and among less experienced doctors, whereas DL is linked to a lower rate of oesophageal intubations. Nonetheless, a higher prevalence of arterial hypotension is linked to VL. The possibility and utility profile of VL in comparison to DL in adults was assessed by Hansel J et al¹². With higher rates of successful intubation on the first try and improved glottic views across patient categories and circumstances, they discovered that videolaryngoscopes of any design probably lower the rates

of unsuccessful intubations. The rate of oesophageal intubation is probably lower with hyperangulated designs, and intubation success rates are higher for patients with challenging airway characteristics. While glottic views improved, VL was linked to fewer failure attempts and problems including hypoxaemia in these studies of people undergoing tracheal intubation.

A case of a man who requires surgery under GA due to a glottic lesion was described by Ottoveggio G. et al¹³. He is a challenging intubation patient, according to the anesthesiologic pre-operative examination. Thus, the initial attempt at intubation was carried out in a supine posture using a videolaryngoscope in conjunction with FFS. No evidence of intubation-related damage was discovered after surgery. They came to the conclusion that a videolaryngoscope in conjunction with FFS is safe, helpful, and advised in cases of restricted airways and laryngeal lesions that make it difficult to see the glottic plane. Lewis SR et al¹⁴ assessed if videolaryngoscopes, as opposed to direct laryngoscopy, lower intubation failure and complications in people. They observed that, even in people with expectedly difficult airways, videolaryngoscopy decreased the number of unsuccessful intubations. Although fewer studies documented these results, there was no proof of a decrease in hypoxia or mortality. Hoarseness and laryngeal/airway damage were reduced with videolaryngoscopes. Usually utilizing an intubation difficulty score, videolaryngoscopy decreased difficult viewing and intubation difficulties while increasing simple laryngeal views. While unskilled users did not observe a decrease in failed intubations, expert operators did. They found no difference in the frequency of sore throats and the number of first efforts. Meta-analysis was hampered by the intubation data's temporal heterogeneity. They discovered proof that various videolaryngoscope designs performed differently. Indirect laryngoscopic vs fiberoptic intubation under local anesthesia and sedation seems inadequate, according to Kramer A et al¹⁵. With the videolaryngoscope, the median intubation time was substantially less—38 seconds as opposed to 94 seconds. The anesthetists' and patients' satisfaction levels and intubation success rates were identical. They came to the conclusion that a videolaryngoscope is a suitable substitute for fiberoptic intubation in cases of expected difficulty with nasal intubation.

The use of fiberoptic bronchoscopy and videolaryngoscopy for awake intubation of the trachea was compared by Alhomary M. et al¹⁶. Using videolaryngoscopy instead of fiberoptic bronchoscopy resulted in a reduced intubation time. Neither the failure rate nor the first attempt success rate differed significantly between the two methods. The two groups' levels of patient satisfaction were comparable. Low oxygen saturation and hoarseness/sore throat, two adverse events that were recorded, did not vary. In conclusion, a shorter intubation time is linked to videolaryngoscopy for awake tracheal intubation. Additionally, it appears to have a safety profile and success rate similar to fiberoptic bronchoscopy. For awake intubation, Merola R et al¹⁷ contrasted fiberoptic bronchoscopy with videolaryngoscopy. They showed that, in comparison to fiberoptic bronchoscopy, videolaryngoscopy reduced the length of intubation; this result was supported by subgroup analysis based on the kind of videolaryngoscope. Additionally, the chance of having a saturation below 90% during the treatment was somewhat reduced using videolaryngoscopy. There were no statistically significant differences between the two methods in terms of sore throat/hoarseness, failure intubation, or initial successful intubation attempt. A pooled analysis of patient-reported satisfaction was not possible because different studies used different evaluation techniques to measure this outcome. Last but not least, trial sequential analysis (TSA) for intubation time confirmed that this evidence was conclusive; however, TSA for secondary outcomes did not produce conclusive evidence, suggesting that further trials are

required. They came to the conclusion that, in comparison to fiberoptic bronchoscopy, videolaryngoscopy for awake tracheal intubation reduces intubation duration and the chance of saturation below 90%. In cases of unexpectedly difficult intubation, Kim SH et al¹⁸ used video recording to assess the usefulness of the Bonfils intubation fiberscope assisted by direct laryngoscopy (BIFDL) and the flexible fiberoptic bronchoscope assisted by direct laryngoscopy (FOB-DL) in terms of the time needed to visualize the vocal cords and insert the endotracheal tube. They found that the BIF-DL group had considerably lower T1, T2, and T total. In two instances, intubation with BIF-DL was not feasible; nevertheless, the process was successfully completed with a fiberoptic bronchoscope. They came to the conclusion that while BIF-DL can expedite the intubation of difficult airways, the scope may not always be able to do so. In patients who were expected to have a difficult intubation, Rosenstock CV et al¹⁹ compared awake FFI with awake McGrath video laryngoscope (MVL) intubation. The median time to tracheal intubation was 62 seconds and 80 seconds with FFI. The first-time intubation success rates for FFI and MVL were 79% and 71%, respectively. For ease of intubation, FFI and MVL had median VAS of 2 and 1, respectively. For all methods, the median VAS for patients' evaluations of discomfort was 2, FFI, MVL. In patients with expected difficult airway, they observed no difference in the time to intubation of the trachea among awake FFI and awake MVL intubation carried out by skilled anesthesiologists.

In thoracic surgery patients with anticipated difficult airways, Hu HZ et al²⁰ investigated the clinical efficacy of visual laryngoscopy in conjunction with fiberoptic bronchoscopy guided double lumen tracheal tube intubation. The FVL group experienced a much shorter intubation time than the VL and F groups, and their first-time intubation success rate was significantly greater than that of the F and VL groups. Compared to the F and VL groups, the FVL group's placement time was much shorter. Compared to the F group, the FVL and VL groups had substantially fewer patients with Cormack-Lehane grades I–II. Compared to the VL group, the FVL and F groups experienced a considerably lower rate of postop sore throat. Visual laryngoscopy in conjunction with fiberoptic bronchoscopy increased the favorable rate of first time intubation and reduced the intubation and position time in patients with difficult airways and high airway risk indices who need double lumen endotracheal intubation. Comparing the effectiveness of flexible videoscope (FV), video laryngoscope (VL), and video stylet (VS) devices for intubating patients with challenging airways was the goal of Zhang T et al²¹. They reported that while the first-pass intubation success rate was comparable across Groups VS and FV, it was considerably higher in Groups VS and FV than in Group VL. Compared to Groups VS and FV, Group VL had fewer patients classified as Wilson-Cormack-Lehane grades I–II. Compared to Groups VL and VS, Group FV's time to intubation of the trachea was noticeably greater. Regarding unfavorable intubation responses, there were no discernible variations between the three groups. They asserted that the flexible videoscope and video stylet produce a higher first pass intubation rate of success and more apparent glottic exposure than the usage of the video laryngoscope, and that using the video stylet has the advantage of a comparatively shorter intubation time in patients with difficult airways that require intubation.

Conclusion

For anesthesiologists, managing problematic airways continues to be one of the most important issues. In contrast to video laryngoscopy, this study showed that FFS is a very safe, effective, and repeatable method for managing airways. This method has proven very helpful even in situations of unexpected difficulties since it requires less time and can be used to a wide range of patient characteristics. By reducing bleeding and tissue damage, the approach helps to optimize surgical circumstances and is especially helpful in instances with complicated anatomy.

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